

References

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**Phenol-Formaldehyde Cationic Matrices
substituted by Wheat Husk Charcoal**

T. DHEIVEGAN** and S. KRISHNAMOORTHY*

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College,
Tiruchirappalli-620 015

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SYNTHETIC ion-exchangers are used in analytical chemistry, hydrometallurgy and water treatment¹.

Many ion-exchangers owe their origin to petroleum products and there is a continual increase in their cost. It is, therefore, necessary to prepare cheaper exchangers to identify substitutes which

can partly replace the polymeric content of the exchangers to a considerable extent without causing deterioration of the properties of the parent polymers. Attempts have been made in this laboratory² to synthesise newer cationic exchangers from renewable source of materials. The present work is an attempt to prepare and study the properties of sulphonated phenol-formaldehyde cation-exchangers substituted partially by sulphonated charcoal obtained from wheat husk charcoal.

Experimental

Phenol, formaldehyde (B.D.H.), concentrated sulphuric acid (sp. gr. 1.82) and wheat husk (obtained from local market) were used.

Preparation of the samples: Concentrated H₂SO₄ (12.5 ml) was added slowly to phenol (10 ml) with constant cooling. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 3 h, cooled immediately in ice and kept overnight. Wheat husk was carbonised and sulphonated by adding concentrated H₂SO₄, heating on a water-bath for about 6 h, washing free from acids and drying at 70° overnight. Calculated quantities of sulphonated wheat husk charcoal were added to phenolsulphonic acid so as to keep the percentage substitution of wheat husk charcoal respectively at 0, 20, 25, 30, 35 and 40. Each mixture was polymerised with formaldehyde (12.5 ml) at 70°, ground and sieved (samples labelled A to F).

A separate sample of sulphonated wheat husk charcoal after purification was subjected to these studies as such (sample G).

Physical measurements: The absolute density of the resin in both the hydrated and dehydrated states was determined by using specific gravity bottle in water and in a non-aqueous medium (toluene), respectively (Table 1).

The gravimetry swelling measurements were made by allowing the samples to equilibrate in water overnight. The weight of the swollen sample (net weight) was taken as M_w and the weight of the corresponding dry sample was taken as M_d . The

TABLE 1 - PERCENTAGE SWELLING, ABSOLUTE DENSITY, ATTRITION PERCENTAGE AND EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF DIFFERENT RESIN COMPOSITES

Sample	Husk-charcoal in resin %	Average swelling %	Absolute density		% Attrition*	Exchange column capacity meq g ⁻¹			
			Hydrated state	Dehydrated state		Na ⁺	Ca ⁺⁺	Zn ⁺⁺	Mg ⁺
A	0	124	1.65	1.51	22.99	0.701	1.137	1.028	1.002
B	20	114	1.50	1.49	21.18	0.694	1.128	1.017	0.994
C	25	97	1.47	1.46	19.17	0.678	1.062	1.014	0.971
D	30	82.5	1.44	1.42	18.80	0.585	0.997	0.914	0.857
E	35	80	1.39	1.33	18.50	0.500	0.865	0.820	0.765
F	40	76.4	1.34	1.22	16.40	0.414	0.748	0.685	0.682
G	100	57.1	1.21	1.12	10.79	0.428	0.438	0.385	0.314

*Amount passed through 200 mesh sieve after shaking.

**Present address: Tamil University, Tanjore.

gravimetric percent swelling (α) was calculated from the equation,

$$\alpha = \frac{M_w - M_d}{M_d} \times 100$$

Swelling percentage for various samples are given in Table 1.

Attrition percentage: The percentage attrition of different samples was determined and compared with each other. The particles in each sample were separated into two sizes, >200 mesh and <200 mesh. Particles >200 mesh size were shaken for several hours and again the particles >200 mesh in size were separated. From the weights of the particles before and after shaking, the attrition effect was calculated for each sample and the values were compared (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The average percentage swelling decreases as the percentage of wheat husk charcoal in the resin increases. The swelling percentage of the pure resin is higher than other samples. As the charcoal is added, the porous nature decreases and so also the swelling capacity. The absolute densities of the pure resin and the composites in the hydrated state are less than those in the dehydrated state. In both the states the absolute densities decrease for the pure resin. The attrition effect of the various samples decreases from sample A to F and this is due to the formation of the resin in the capillaries of charcoal particles.

It is observed that the exchange capacities for Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Ca^{2+} ions are greater than those for Na^+ ion for all composites. The sizes of the hydrated ions and Na ions are comparable. Therefore, the higher exchange capacity for the divalent ions, mentioned here, is due to the ionic charge. Among the divalent cations, the exchange capacity increases from Mg^{2+} to Ca^{2+} ion. This may be due to the decrease in the hydrated ionic sizes from Mg to Ca ions. The exchange capacity slowly decreases upto 25% of the charcoal and thereafter the decrease is sudden. Thus it may be concluded that the substitution of charcoal upto 25% results in the exchange capacities as that of the pure resin and hence may be used instead of pure resin for economical reasons.

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Stereochemistry of the Oxime of *N*-Hydroxyimide of β -Naphthol - Maleic Anhydride Adduct

ASHOK KUMAR SINGH* and S. K. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee,
Roorkee-247 667

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LANTHANIDE reagents have been used in the stereochemical investigation of organic molecules¹⁻³ including aliphatic and alicyclic ketoximes^{4,5}. Anisotropy of the hydroxyimino group produces large chemical shift differences between *syn*- and *anti*-protons⁶. The effect of anisotropy of oximido group is attributed^{7,8} to the hydroxyl group which deshields the neighbouring protons. In this study, an attempt has been made for the first time to determine stereochemistry of the oxime (1) of *N*-hydroxyimide of β -naphtholmaleic anhydride adduct by nmr study using $Eu(DPM)_3$ as shift reagent. ¹H nmr spectrum of 1 exhibited multiplets at δ 7.27 (4 $\times$ ArH), 4.17 (H-1), 3.90 (H-4), 3.40 (H-2 and H-3), 2.63 (H₁₀-10) and a broad singlet at 3.87 for two hydroxyl protons.

1

Successive addition of $Eu(DPM)_3$ in 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, 0.20, 0.30, and 0.40 *M* equivalent to substrate led to downfield shifts of ¹H signals and the plots of induced downfield shifts ($\Delta\delta$) vs the LSR concentration, $[Eu(DPM)_3]/[substrate]$, for each of H-1, H-10, and H-2 resonances showed linearity (Fig. 1).

TABLE 1 - PARAMAGNETIC SHIFTS OF PROTONS RESONANCES OF COMPOUND 1 AT VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS OF $Eu(DPM)_3$

Concn. of $Eu(DPM)_3$ *	$\Delta\delta$			
	H-1	H-2	H-10	H-4
0.05	11	5	3	0
0.10	33	14	9	2
0.15	54	23	15	4
0.20	75	32	21	7
0.30	134	52	33	11
0.40	181	73	46	17

*Concentration in mole ratio of LSR to substrate.